

Best Fit Learning Modalities: The Home Economics Teachers' Trepidations

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Abstract. This study explored the varied understandings of the home economics teachers in their search for the best fit learning modalities as well as their trepidations in implementing the new normal modalities. There were eight (8) home economics teachers who participated in the study coming from the Division of Davao City. This study made use of a phenomenological approach to extract the ideas of the home economics teachers. The participants were purposely selected as representatives from the teachers in the same division. The in-depth-interview was employed to gather information as regards to their respective experiences in their quest for the best fit learning modalities in home economics subject. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged as pertains to the trepidations of the teachers: undefined teaching strategies; planning variety of lessons, limited skills development and limited home cooking gadgets. The coping mechanisms of the HE teachers in averting their problems revealed the following themes: to enhance theory an online activities and open learning concept. As to the educational management insights gathered from the participants, the following insights emerged: resourcefulness and creativity of the HE teachers, proper work planning and upgrading of on line skills. The home economics teachers may be more proactive and developing more of their technological skills to address their individual difficulties in dealing their technology driven students. By getting along with the speed of the students in doing things on line, they may also be redirected to learn more from the vast opportunities provided by the on line information.

KEY WORDS

1. Best fit learning modalities 2. home economics 3. trepidations of teachers

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1. Introduction

Home economics education has always been dynamic. Teaching methodologies in this discipline did not stop and lingered. This discipline propelled in exact direction as other disciplines in the learning curriculum had to go. The teaching of home economics does not only concern itself with food and nutrition. Today's direction is not simply content or topic oriented, but it comes along with the tedious academic preparations, technological abilities of the teachers as well as adapting to the current food technologies. It is well known that time spent learning, or learning time, is one of the most reliable predictors of opportunity to learn. In the United States, researchers have documented the effects of 'summer learning loss' demonstrating that ex-

tended interruption of one's studies causes not only a suspension of learning time, but causes a loss of knowledge and skills gained. Pandemic is likely to generate the greatest disruption in educational opportunity worldwide in a generation. This disruption will impact the livelihoods of individuals, and the prospects of their communities. It is imperative, for this reason, that education leaders take immediate steps to develop and implement strategies which mitigate the educational impact of the Pandemic. Clearly define roles and expectations for teachers to effectively steer and support students' learning in the new situation, through direct instruction where possible or guidance for self-directed learning. The role of teachers is essential to the success of the learning experience, even more so than the physical environment of schools or the technological infrastructure. When the structuring power of time and place that schools provide, dissolves and online learning becomes the dominant mode, the role of teachers does not diminish, quite on the contrary. Through direct instruction or through guidance provided in self-directed learning, in synchronous or asynchronous modes, the teacher remains essential in steering students' learning. (Reimers, Fernando M. and Schleicher, Andreas, 2020). The DepEd recognizes the importance of professional standards in the continuing professional development and advancement of teachers based on the principle of lifelong learning. It is committed to supporting teachers, and taking cognizance of unequivocal evidence that good teachers are vital to raising student achievement. Quality learning is contingent upon quality teaching. Hence, enhancing teacher quality becomes of utmost importance for long term and sustainable nation building. The changes brought about by various national and global frameworks such as the K to 12 Reform, ASEAN Integration, globalization, and the changing character of the 21st century learners necessitate the improvements and call for the rethinking of the National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS); hence, the development of the PPST (DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017). Abucayon, R. et al (2016) cited the speech of former education secretary Br. Armin Luistro FSC - Secretary of the Department of Education- during the annual meeting of the Philippines Business for Education last March 2012. There is a constant need to determine the efficacy and the readiness of every education student about to depart from their respective alma maters into the challenging and demanding world of knowledge instruction. The new trends and fads of the age also add up to the challenge of teaching young minds thus magnifying the scope of needed skills that each aspiring young teacher must possess. This immense need for mastery of the skills is a determining asset to teachers particularly in the elementary level since the learners of this stage do not possess what we call as the maturity of the mind as compared to learners of the secondary level, thus there is this urge pinpoint of the attention towards the incoming elementary teachers who are currently having their practice teaching as of this school year. Elementary student provides the challenge of applying the principles of teaching especially in terms of classroom management since little children are likely to fidget and roam around and immature fights among pupils are likely to erupt. In the local scenario, it can be noted that a lot of teachers now have various problems faced amidst the pandemic crisis. While there are several on line trainings and seminars given for free, teachers still are apprehensive whether they have enough teaching skills to deal with the demands of this time. Particularly, there is a need to adapt to the new normal in the classroom. Teachers are not assured that what they know in the past could still be viable at this point in time. The teachers are now concerned with their respective abilities to deliver the contents of the curriculum based on the suggested teaching modalities. They are not

really sure how well can they interact with their students. The home economics teachers are apprehensive whether what they will use as the teaching modality is fit to the kind to students they have. It is in these premise that I am conducting this study to dig up some of the issues of home economics teachers particularly in our place in Baguio District, Calinan, Davao City. As a researcher, I have known so much about the capacity of our school to deliver the necessary content as demanded by the curriculum. I am familiar with the common teaching method-

ologies of the home economics teachers in our locality and it has been on the same manner since then. With the new normal, I have some significant concerns and hesitations about the best fit teaching modalities in our area. What the teachers might be thinking as the best fit teaching modalities may not give the expected results. It is premised in this study that I could provide a brighter idea on the ways in identifying what is best for our school and the students as well.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study is to explore the narratives and insights of the home economics teachers on their best fit teaching modalities and how these modalities challenge them as well as how they cope with some concerns or problems arising in implementing different types of teaching approaches in delivering their subject matter to their students. It is hoped that the findings of the study will enlighten the home economics teachers based on the participants responses during the interview from Baguio District, Calinan, Davao City.

1.2. Research Questions—

- (1) What are the trepidations of home economics teachers in determining the best fit teaching modalities in their school?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of the home economics teachers in averting their problems?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from their trepidations?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Best Fit Teaching Modalities – this refers to the kind of teaching modality that will be adapted by the home economics teachers involved in this study. Teach-

ers' trepidations. – This refers to the fears and apprehensions of home economics teachers as they implement the new mode of learning by using the modular or on line approach. This also means how the home economics teachers tried their best to search for the best fit learning modalities.

1.4. Significant of the Study—To clearly determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings will be addressed, the following persons or agencies will be the beneficiaries. Department of Education. The DepEd, particularly the District of Baguio, Calinan, Davao City, may improve or revisit the policies and guidelines in determining the best fit teaching

modalities in their district. Secondary teachers. For the secondary teachers to be more alert and sensitive in determining the best fit teaching modalities in their own school with due consideration their capacity to deliver the curriculum contents. The students. That they may be able to embrace the new normal of learning, taking into consideration their teachers new skills and schools capacity in delivering quality education.

1.5. *Theoretical Lens*—This study is based on the theory popularized by Chunk, (2012) on the Behavioral learning theories view learning as change in rate/frequency of occurrence, or form of behavior or response which occurs primarily as a function of environmental factors. They also contend that learning involves the formation of associations between stimuli and responses. Behaviorists explain learning in terms of observable phenomena, and reinforcing consequences make the response more likely to occur whereas punishing consequences make it less likely. The role of environment specifically how stimuli are arranged and presented and how responses are reinforced are of most important. Motivation is the process whereby goal-directed activities are instigated and sustained. As environment properly arranged help learning to occur, teachers should prepare the environment that will help learners to learn such as arranging activities that suit environment. Teachers also need to help learners make practice of what they have learned. This is important as learning is subject to the rate of occurrence of behavior. The practicing is important for strengthening the responses This study is further anchored on the proposition of Secretary Leonor Briones (2020) who said that the Department of Education (DepEd) has prepared various alternative learning delivery modalities as a response to COVID-19 situation in the country. Briones, in an online press conference, allayed the fears and concerns of parents and learners who might not have access to technology due to lack of gadgets or devices. “We will offer more than just online learning,” she said. When classes for School Year (SY) 2020-2021 formally start in August, Briones said that DepEd will provide Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) with the alternative learning delivery modalities to be offered for various types of learners nationwide. “The SLMs and the other alternative learning delivery modalities are in place to address the needs, situations, and resources of each and every learner and will cover all the bases in ensuring that basic education will be accessible amid the present crisis posed by COVID-19,” Briones said. Briones explained that the integration of SLMs with the alternative learning delivery modalities (modular, television-based, radio-based instruction, blended, and online) will help DepEd “ensure that all learners have access to quality basic education for SY 2020-2021 with face-to-face classes still prohibited due to the public health situation.” This study is based on the proposition of Keckan, D. (2020). He believed that many Instructional Designers have found that using only one modality or delivery method for a project isn’t effective. People have different learning preferences and it’s not as simple as “Cara prefers visual content, and Jose prefers hands-on practice.” The truth is: learners’ preferences change depending on the information or task they’re learning. How can you meet everyone’s needs, achieve objectives, and stay within budget? Savy Instructional Designers have turned to blended learning because it offers a more efficient learning experience and increased learner engagement, which leads to improved learner performance and measurable results. If designed properly, blended learning is focused on giving learners more autonomy in how and when they are trained rather than following a strict schedule of activities. Blended learning is flexible, allowing the designer to revise and customize all or parts of the training as needed. Lastly, blended learning is more than just adding technology to classroom training. It builds a seamless learning experience using a variety of delivery methods to offer personalized training that helps them achieve learning objectives and business goals efficiently.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design that was used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection, the data analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical consideration. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviours in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals’ personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, “What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people? “the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of home economics teachers in choosing the best fit teaching modalities in their respective classrooms Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. A good research – undertaking with the selection of the topic, problem or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces ‘paradigm ‘ back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an action of submitting to a view. This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln

(2000) who defend a research paradigms a “basic set of belief that guide action”, dealing with first principles, “ultimates’ or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012) reality is a subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realist exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, realities as to the experiences of the secondary teachers in selecting what they think as the best fit teaching modalities for their students. In this study, I relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidences of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure reliability of result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precludes from making personal bias as the study progress. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible as during the study in order obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985) as cited by Creswell (2013) state that on epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an “insider.” Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011).I will identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual

researchers “hold explicit belief”. The intention of this research is to gather the details on the experiences of the home economics teachers in identifying the best fit teaching modalities and to check whether these are parallel to their respective teaching proficiencies as they used to have. I assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that will shed light to the knowledge behind the inquiry particularly on the teacher’s experiences and challenges they have encountered in the course of their selection of what they think as the best fit teaching modalities in their respective schools. Axiology refers to role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes own interpretation in conjunction with interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. I therefore preserve the merit of the participant’s answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant’s personal interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and uses qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in explaining the experiences of the home economics teachers in selecting the best fit teaching modalities in congruence with their teaching proficiencies. As a researcher, I agree with the post modernism philosophy of Afzal-os-sadat Hossieni (2011). I believe that the aims of education are teaching critical thinking, production of knowledge, development of individual and social identity, self-creation. In postmodern education teachers just lead students to discover new things. They provide opportunities to discuss about different subjects and make creative

ways. In this situation student learn to listen to other voices. They tolerate others criticism and try to think in critical way. They learn to respect other cultures and nationalities. Also they emphasize on cooperative learning independent

learning, and dialectic, critical and verbal methods. It is deduced that postmodernism and creativity are embedded in each other and we can find the result of this opinion in postmodern education.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology is different from method. Methodology is creative and responsive approach to understand questions and subject matter while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study the experiences of the home economics teachers in choosing the best fit teaching modalities in their classes in Baguio District, Calinan, Davao City. The researcher’s inquisitiveness on the experiences of the home economics teachers became the basis for doing this qualitative research, a means of which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and phenomena”. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the home economics teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols and meaning of the experiences will be presented. Phenomenological research is based

on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology which concerns with that “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher hoped that the subjective experiences and perspectives of the home economics teachers s they choose the so called best fit teaching modalities are explored and insights were drawn for possible future researches.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study used a qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994). The data was then read and reread and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this pro-

cess the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation or experiences and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. In this study phenomenology attempts to extract the most pure, untainted data and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing is used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is memoing (Maxwell, 2013).

2.4. *Research Participants*—

The participants in this study were composed of eight (8) home economics teachers as informants. The selected informants were coming from different secondary schools in Baguio District, Davao City. All the informants must have at least three (3) years experience in teaching home economics, they may either be class advisers or floating teachers and are major in Home economics. I used qualitative analyses typically required a smaller sample size the quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should not be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions led to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurred when adding more participants to the study did not result in

2.5. Role of the Researcher—My role as researcher in this study was to attempt to access the thoughts and feelings of study participants. This involved asking informants to talk about things that may be very personal to them. Sometimes the experiences being explored are fresh in the participant's mind, whereas on other occasions

2.6. Data Collection—According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process is to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they provided good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data such as interview or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called "field issues," which may be a problem, such as

additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommended the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommended five (5) to 25 and Morse (1994) suggested at least six (6). There were no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990). Furthermore, I participated in the interpretation of narrative exposition of my participants. I kept their identity in a confidential manner, Hence, their answers were recorded properly.

reliving past experiences may be difficult. However the data are being collected, a primary responsibility of the researcher is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins.

having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, there are seven steps in the process of data collection. First is the site or individual; the participants were the home economics teachers in the secondary level from Baguio District, Calinan, Davao City. Second is the access and rapport; letter from the Dean of the Graduate School is given to the graduate student for the approval of the division superintendent; letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal and the concerned elemen-

tary teachers were prepared for easy collection of data. The third is the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants have experienced the phenomenon being studied. There were eight (8) informants selected in this study. The selected home economics teachers were considered group of individuals who can best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered as individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the collection of data. The fourth is the forms of data; the process of collecting information involved primarily in the In Depth Interview (IDI) with the eight (8) informants. The fifth is the recording procedures; the use of a protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form used to record information collected during an observation or interview. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last was the storing of data; Davidson's (1996) suggested the use of database in backing

up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. The data was collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time, therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippines which was convened in January 2020. The Collection of data or the In Depth Interview (IDI) was conducted following the protocols for Social Distancing which is one of the mandates of IATF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. In this study, the IDI was conducted with utmost care so that social distancing is followed and that at least 2 meters between persons was made. For some participants who missed the face to face social distancing efforts, the videocall via messenger, viber, zoom or google meet was used to gather the data or responses of the participants.

2.7. *Data Analysis*—In this study all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analysed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how individual were experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called "meaning units" or themes. She wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, he wrote a description of

"how" the experience happened. This was called "structural description," and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the "essence" of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is that it's a flexible method which can be d both for explorative studies, where the researcher do not have a clear idea of what patterns is being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher know exactly what he or she is are interested in. No matter which type of study is being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis

is that the researcher respects the data and try to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Document analysis. Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a systematic procedure to analyse documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data in order to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a larger qualitative or mixed methods study, where it is often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). When used in triangulation, documents can corroborate or refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources, which helps to guard against bias (Frey, Bruce B., 2018). Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. This is a way of assur-

ing the validity of research through the use of a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. However, the purpose of triangulation is not necessarily to cross-validate data but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation - The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations and other factors such as time, day, season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors then validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirements as mentioned is the use of environmental triangulation best suit the environment of the research being conducted

2.8. *Framework of Analysis*—According to Braun and Clark (2006) methods of qualitative data analysis fall in two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) and methods which are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks , such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across a range of different theoretical and epistemological approaches and are therefore very flexible. One such method

is thematic analysis, which through the theoretical freedom “provides flexible and useful research tool, which can potentially provide a rich and detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun and Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my own resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I use several nights to listen to the interviews to deepen my understanding on the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay-out and con-

ventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved, and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step as data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used a number of different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts, the framework technique as developed by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003). This technique was useful to me in the process of coding, sorting and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedure included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could

be cross referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with coded being the most basic segments of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub themes; Phase 5. I defined and named themes, making sure they give the reader immediate sense of what the theme is all about. Phase 6. I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes), used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments in relation to the research question.

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness is all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability. In qualitative study, trustworthiness is very important because the result and finding of the research study would depend on the process of how it is being conducted by the researcher. Trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details are required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility is how confident the qualitative researcher is in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you

do is essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues which ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue is "how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so." Transferability is how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study's findings are applicable to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using graphic organizer as strategy in teaching reading comprehension. The use of graphic organizer as a strategy in teaching read-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

ing comprehension is effective in the domains analysis and creating. With this, the researcher is interested to know the students' perspective of using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader is able to provide generalization of the study based on his own context and can able to address that core issue of "how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory." Confirmability is the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants' responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability is based on the acknowledgement that research is never objective. Dependability is the extent that the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher can use inquiry audit in order to establish dependability which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis in order to ensure that the findings are consistent and could be repeated. In this component, the use of database is very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected must be properly kept for future use as references. Gasson (2004) states that dependability deals with the core issue that "the way in which

a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques." Ethical Consideration Considering the nature of qualitative studies, the interaction between researchers and participants can be ethically challenging for the former, as they are personally involved in different stages of the study. Therefore, formulation of specific ethical guidelines in this respect is essential. The relationship and intimacy that is established between the researchers and participants in qualitative studies can raise a range of different ethical concerns, and qualitative researchers face dilemmas such as respect for privacy, establishment of honest and open interactions, and avoiding misrepresentations. Richards and Schwartz (2002) emphasizes that a fundamental ethical requirement of all research should be scientifically sound. The research must be properly designed and carried out by researchers with adequate levels of expertise and supervision. It should be worth doing in a sense that the result generates tangible benefits. In addition, Sanjari (2014) informed that consent has been recognized as an integral part of ethics in research carried out in different fields. For qualitative researchers, it is of the utmost importance to specify in advance which data will be collected and how they are to be used. He also stated that informed consent is a prerequisite for all research involving identifiable subjects, except in cases where an ethics committee judges that such consent is not possible and where it is felt that the benefits of the research outweigh the potential harm. A minimum requirement for an interview study should be that written consent be obtained from the participant after they have been informed, verbally and in writing, about the following issues: the purpose and scope of the study, the types of questions which are likely to be asked, the use to which the results put, the method of anonymization and the extent to which participants' utterances will be used in reports. Participants should also be given time to both consider

their participation and to ask questions of the researcher. In this study, I would follow the ethical considerations as part of the process in a qualitative research. It was the responsibility of the researcher to completely inform the participants about the different aspects of the research in comprehensible language. The needed clarifications include the following issues: nature

of the study, the participants' potential role, the identity of the researcher, the objective of the research, and how the results will be published and used. In same manner, this study submitted to the ethics committee of the Rizal Memorial College, graduate school for verification and approval.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the research dealt with the research questions that seeks the answers from the participants. The participants divulged their experiences in selecting the best fit learning modalities in their respective home economics classes as well as their trepidations in the current academic delivery during the pandemic time where face to face learning home economics is not allowed. This part of the research elaborates the narrations of the home economics teachers as they implementer the curriculum.

3.1. The trepidations of home economics teachers in determining the best fit teaching modalities in their school—Some of the fears and anxieties of the home economics teachers

were narrated by the participants during the actual interview as to what they really feel in conducting the home economics classes on line and modular modes.

3.1.1. Undefined teaching strategies—Most of the participants clearly cited that they have undergone different experiences while conducting their classes. They could hardly determine which of the available strategies can possibly be used as there were several issues the popped out during the class hours.

The narrations of the teachers clearly suggests that the teacher are very much worried whether their students can still cope with their lessons at home. They were also worried if their chosen teaching strategy in delivering the learning plans can facilitate the learning pf the students. Some participants even mentioned that the on line learning and teaching approach is not even the best way to deliver the lessons. Even if modules were also provided, this does not guarantee that learning home economics will take place. They vocalized that on line learning and teaching modality is not the best option in teaching home economics. It can be cleaned from the

statements of the participants that they were experiencing some discomfort in delivering their lessons during the pandemic season. One participant said that she hopes that her learners will pick up something from the daily lessons. Participant number 8 utterly described her feelings that some of their students cannot perform all the prescribed activities at home due to lack of materials and equipments. She is very much worried the the students skills is at stake, and that these expected skills may not totally develop. In a study conducted by Margolis, Jason and Higgins Christine (2012) concluded that the Hybrid Teacher Leader (HTL) are teachers whose official schedule includes both teaching K–12 students and leading teachers in some capacity. a pervasive lack of role definition for the HTLs amid heightened organizational complexity, leading to numerous existing definitions emerging. Conflicting definitions led to diminished success for the HTLs, relationship deterior-

ration, a reversion to professional development removed from the classroom, and a lack of capacity to account for HTL efficacy. The scientific reviews as published by Paul Kirschner and others in *Educational Psychologist* (2006) as cited by Reville, William (2015) claim that the new methods are far less effective at imparting knowledge to students than whole-class teach-

3.1.2. Planning variety of lessons—The use and planning of variety of lessons is one of the most significant act that a teacher would do. There is a need to address the specific needs of each learner inside the classroom. However, it is easier said than done. Most of these participants were assigned not only one but two or more subjects in one grade level alone. This does not include other grade levels where the teachers needs to attend to. Planning variety of lessons is a tedious task for teachers especially if there are several classes that needs to be attended to. The fears of the two participants in this study obviously shows that they are worried, particularly on the learning materials available in their respective homes. Though, participant two stated that she prepared several activities to allow them to explore at their own means on how to do and perform the activities at home. Participant three stated that it is like a guessing game. She was thinking of a more appropriate teaching modality for the students and herself. Kean.edu.com (Accessed November 2020) cited that Good lesson planning is essential to the process of teaching and learning. A teacher who is prepared is well on his/her way to a successful instructional experience. The development of interesting lessons takes a great deal of time and effort. As a new teacher you must be committed to spending the necessary time in this endeavour. It is also important to

3.1.3. Limited skills development—Most of the informants of the study were one in say-

ing methods. Nevertheless, academic education- alists have successfully resisted any reintroduc- tion of whole-class teaching methods. However, the climate is changing. Following the teachers' visit to China, Britain's minister for education Nick Gibbs told the *Mail on Sunday*: "I would like to see schools adopt whole-class teaching methods, particularly in maths and science."

realize that the best planned lesson is worth- less if interesting delivery procedures, along with good classroom management techniques, are not in evidence. There is a large body of research available pertaining to lesson develop- ment and delivery and the significance of class- room management. They are skills that must be researched, structured to your individual style, implemented in a teacher/learning situation, and constantly evaluated and revamped when neces- sary. Consistency is of the utmost importance in the implementation of a classroom management plan. All teachers should understand that they are not an island unto themselves. The educa- tional philosophy of the district and the unique- ness of their schools should be the guiding force behind what takes place in the classroom. The school's code of discipline, which should be fair, responsible and meaningful, must be reflected in every teacher's classroom management efforts. According to Amaro, Marie (2020) she was as- tonished not that students were off task or diffi- cult but that they were attentive and compliant for so long when they were expected to sit and listen to teachers talking . The tasks they were asked to do were not inviting or challenging or motivating. There was much off task behaviour and disruption could be prevented through the use of relevant, engaging curriculum and inter- esting pedagogy. Making the learning more interesting for the students will also increase your enjoyment.

ing that distance learning or out of the school learning of home economics will have drastic

effects on the skills development of the students. Learning home economics at home will limit the exposure and actual demonstrations conducted by the teachers at school. There are also issues on the how the skills are demonstrated, whether the students is doing the right thing as required in the cooking procedures. There are very limited assessment on their skills and the worst is that, the students are not performing the activity at home. Pictures and snap shots of their student outputs is not a guarantee that the skills of the students has been improved. Bryant, Atarra (2018) said that having the knowledge of how to cook and manage aspects of a household through a class is vital in today's society. Although many may think that a class isn't needed to teach about the basic necessities, having a class solely devoted to these aspects is exactly what we need in school. Things like learning how to make more than a grilled cheese or how to sew is something that everyone should learn at a young age. Home economic classes weren't taught until the early 20th century. An example that had the most impact was the "Treatise on Domestic Economy for the Use of Young Ladies at Home," written by Catharine Beecher. Beecher argued that it was important to teach domestic life and apply scientific principles to things like cooking and housekeeping. Home economic classes would help teens develop skills in family financing, nutrition, cooking and other various skills for life. Not only does home economics teach students about cooking and safety but it also builds responsibility. It teaches teens to use the techniques they learned in class in their home life. When teens learn how to take care of their household and themselves, it helps them to become more responsible at home. Home economics also teaches students how to be savvy consumers. The Home Economics Victoria (2020) underscored that Individuals must have practical opportunities to utilise theoretical knowledge and make informed decisions as a means of developing essential life skills. Many

young people do not receive such opportunities at home to develop practical skills (cooking; food and nutritional literacy; health and lifestyle choices), risk-management skills and strategies for managing their own wellbeing. Home economics education facilitates the development of knowledge and skills to assist with the development of independent, resourceful consumer citizens capable of making informed decisions and establishing work/life balance. We believe this is achievable by engaging and educating young people in a variety of home economics contexts such as food; nutrition and health, consumerism and resource management; human development and family studies.

3.1.4. Limited home cooking gadgets—It is a reality that most of the students enrolled in home economics do not have a complete home cooking gadgets or materials. Most of these student, if not all, are living in a meagre lifestyle and they cannot afford to buy the utensils need to perform the activities prepared for them by their home economics teachers. In most cases, the meal planning requires several kitchen utensils, not found in the common kitchens of the learners. This poses a huge problem in the performance and output of the learners while following the procedures at home. Eventually, the activity will not be successful as expected. Thus, this will even lead to the learner's dismay and loss of interest in home economics. Participants' responses during the conduct of the interview revealed that they were concerned with the lack of cooking gadgets or cooking utensils in the homes of their learners. When the students were given several activities to be performed at home, the home economics teachers were apprehensive whether the activities will be performed well at home. There were times when parents don not bother about the learning activities of their child. For the on line learning assignments, there are also issues on the slow internet connection as mentioned by the participants. Some of the activities were not

Fig. 3. The trepidations of home economics teachers in determining the best fit teaching modalities in their school

sustained due to lack of cooking utensils. A situation where the informants were quite worried in terms of the learning outcomes of their students. Everyone has heard the saying; “the right tool for the right job,” and “you are only as good as your tools.” These sayings are very true when it comes to the choice and use of cooking equipment. The quality of the cooking equipment that you choose to use is as outstanding as the tools themselves when it comes to work and food quality. Given that there is a wide variety of cooking equipment required for an even more extensive range of dishes, it’s essential to make sure that you choose the right types and quality meet your kitchens needs. Kitchen equipment is a great help in maintaining the cleanliness or orderliness in the kitchen (2020

© Tipton Equipment Restaurant Supply). Along with Home-blogger.com (2020) there are things we simply cannot cook, eat or mess around food with, these are the utensils. These enhances the speed of the cooking process, and make serving the food better procedure, in order to maintain the hygienic environment, it is extremely important to have a cook system in place. Few things are as much important as the meals in kitchen. There are some cultures that use their hands while eating more of their food, but in case you are not part of them you may have noticed the idea and reason in using different kitchen utensils. You do not have to be a master chef to know that the good utensils and tools make the process of cooking and consuming food better in this manner.

3.2. *The coping mechanisms of the home economics teachers in averting their problems?*—In this generation, most of the learners have varied skills n cooking. Some of them have

a well-developed cooking skills while some rely so much on their parents prepared meals. Other will opt to buy precooked food or cooked food from neighboring food stalls. These realities

exists almost to all the learners and teachers are more concerned with their moves on how to avert the problems in skills development, especially that learning nowadays is done at home.

3.2.1. Enhance theory and on line activities—Six of the participants stated that they need to undergo some trainings or upgrading of their professional skills. Others opted to do more research to improve their teaching delivery, while one of the participants said that she gave more activities pertaining to the theories which is internet based. Some of the participants tried to reach their students through messenger or on line. Some of them adopted the latest technology available to get in touch with their students. Jonassen Land (2000) posits that a theory of online learning as online participation is a good move and is suggested. The implication of the theory is straightforward: If we want to enhance online learning, we need to enhance online learner participation. Nowadays, most researchers agree that knowledge not only exists in individual minds but also “in the discourse among individuals, the social relationships that bind them, the physical artefacts that they use and produce, and the theories, models and methods they use to produce them”. Research has argued that online learn-

3.2.2. Adopt open learning concept—The participants were generous with their ideas that they were thinking on an open learning concept. Since they cannot fully implement home economics learning standards among their students, they began thinking of the idea that they will open the learning activities for their students. Each learner will have its own interpretation and ways on how to prepare or cook the recipe at hand. Whichever is more appropriate for them and more comfortable at the premises of their homes. It can be noted, from the re-

The home economics teachers are all trying their very best to find solutions to the problems caused by using various teaching modalities.

ing is best accomplished when learners participate and collaborate (Bento Schuster, 2003). There is convincing empirical evidence that supports such statements. In a survey completed by 1,406 online learners at the State University of New York, it was concluded that the results that stand out most clearly for learning effectiveness were: interaction with the teachers; levels of participation compared to classroom; and interaction with classmates (Fredericksen et al. 2000). Hrastinske, Stefan (2009) cited the work of Harasin (1989) who stated that education is inspired by constructivist and social learning theories. Distance learners have traditionally studied more independently because of technical limitations. However, ever since online education emerged, participation has received more attention. It is widely agreed upon that it is critical to enhance participation in online education. Paradoxally, current conceptualizations of participation differ considerably – researchers seem to agree on the importance of online participation even though they do not agree upon the meaning of the concept.

sponses of the participants that they were more focused on the learning styles of the students and that they gave all the opportunities to the students to do things on their own with minimum teacher supervision. They felt that there is a need to fit the learning styles of the students with the lessons. They also agreed that planning and goal setting for the students is a good idea. They were more focused on what is available, simple and useful. They were also united by saying that they need to find solution to the current problems that are practical and useful.

They emphasized that you have to plan your work and work your plan. Berg, Garry (2016) stressed that distance learning, also called distance education, e-learning, and online learning, form of education in which the main elements include physical separation of teachers and students during instruction and the use of various technologies to facilitate student-teacher and student-student communication. Distance learning traditionally has focused on nontraditional students, such as full-time workers, military personnel, and nonresidents or individuals in remote regions who are unable to attend classroom lectures. However, distance learning has become an established part of the educational world, with trends pointing to ongoing growth. Students and institutions embrace distance learning with good reason. Universities benefit by adding students without having to construct classrooms and housing, and students reap the advantages of being able to work where and when they choose. Various terms have been used to describe the phenomenon of distance learning. Strictly speaking, distance learning (the student's activity) and distance teaching

(the teacher's activity) together make up distance education. Common variations include e-learning or online learning, used when the Internet is the medium; virtual learning, which usually refers to courses taken outside a classroom by primary- or secondary-school pupils (and also typically using the Internet); correspondence education, the long-standing method in which individual instruction is conducted by mail; and open learning. Landry, Lauren (2018) stressed that dozens of institutions are rethinking how they deliver education by democratizing access to textbooks, lesson plans, and even courses themselves. It's a movement called open learning that enables students to have greater control over what they learn, where, and when. Open educational resources (OER) also enable students to tap into and explore a field of study in a more approachable, cost-effective way. Educators can take the concept of openness one step further by pursuing open pedagogy, which Matthews-DeNatale (2018) describes as "engaging students in real work that they can share beyond the boundaries of the classroom."

3.3. Educational management insights can be drawn from their trepidations?—The choice of best fit learning modalities this school year 2020-2221 has been a tedious one. Nobody knows what is fit and what is not. The start of this school year was tough enough to stir the

entire educational institutions in the country. Each one was asking, which is the best learning modality that can be offered for the students. This study has unraveled some of the simple thoughts of the home economics teachers as to what is best to deliver their home economics curriculum.

3.3.1. Resourcefulness and creativity—Being resourceful is one of the best characteristics of home economics teachers. They can do meal planning by substituting some ingredients and kitchen utensils. They can also create something in the kitchen without sacrificing the palatability and presentation of the food. Three of the participants confessed that they need to be resourceful

in their respective schools if they want to implement the curricular contents of their subjects in home economics. Knowing the limitations of their schools and the limitations of the resources of the homes of their students, such resourcefulness is a welcome move to allow the students to appreciate the contents and demands of their subject. Creativity comes along with

Fig. 4. The coping mechanisms of the home economics teachers in averting their problems

the teachers’ resourcefulness. Creating something out of what is currently available provides a good avenue to come up with the same product of different features. A great possibility while all the available ingredients in cooking is at the table. Mar, Jeff (2012) cited one TV show ”Chopped” on the Food Network. This cooking show challenges four competing chefs to create dishes in about a half hour. Each chef must work with the same set of ingredients, but no recipe. The secret to winning? It was clearly in using practical creativity and resourcefulness. Bright, Christopher (2020) quoted that “Cooking is one of the best ways to learn important life skills. From research to multitasking, cooking can teach us how to improve the skills we use every day. Nothing else could both teach

life skills and be delicious!”. He identified at least three wayd of doing it: Research, Digging through all these recipes teaches patience and resourcefulness. Looking for a recipe takes time of course, and it can sometimes be difficult to find the exact one you need. You need to be resourceful and carefully select which method would be the most efficient way to find a recipe; Planning, You need to plan and ensure you have all the required ingredients before you can take any more steps forward and Organization, Organizing your utensils, shelves, and other items so they’re in a convenient position for you is a great way to avoid losing vital time cooking and Multitasking, doing multiple tasks while cooking becomes an art in itself.

3.3.2. *Proper work planning*—Proper work planning is a must for home economics teachers. This allows the teachers do things at an organized manner. Having a work plan for the entire school year or even on a particular

grading period permits the teachers to foresee what is beyond and the activities lined up as well as the materials and utensils to be used. With proper work plan, some important ingredients, utensils and other kitchen gadgets can

be changed without altering the final output of the cooking procedure and output. As verbalized by the participants during the interview, they pointed out that proper planning takes time, though time consuming, the teachers are capable of managing their resources. They argued that with proper work planning, activities can still be implemented despite the laboratory limitations of even home utensils are not complete. There are cases wherein a complete set of kitchen gadgets is needed to complete the cooking tasks. Teachers can suggest other alternative ways of doing and performing such tasks at home without sacrificing the quality and taste of the food. Scavetta, Allyssa (2020) pointed out that before one can accomplish his or her goals, they need to plan how to reach them. A work plan creates a clear path to those desired outcomes. Along that path will be resources, constraints and other elements that need to be identified. The work plan won't be written and initiated by a single person. It's a plan of action for a project that should eventually be submitted to board members and stakeholders for approval. Once all is said and done, then you can continue

3.3.3. Upgrading of online skills—On line skills is one of the necessities in this present time. Since almost everything is done on line, there is also a need to upgrade the technology skills of the teachers. Regardless of age, all teachers are bound to learn and unlearn traditional teaching approaches and give a way to the new trends in academic delivery. Majority of the participants described their individual insights for the new normal academic delivery particularly in the field of home economics. There is a clamor from the participants that they need upgrading of their on line skills. What they know is basic computer operations. They are all aware of the rapidly changing learning technologies surrounding them. They felt the need to learn more from what is available in the market, par-

building out the rest of your work plan. When done properly, your work plan will clearly articulate and outline the steps needed to achieve a department-level or company-level end goal by baking in milestones, deliverables, resources, budgetary requirements and a timeline to weave it all together. Ku, Pavel (2018) said that a work plan is a set of goals and processes by which a team can accomplish those goals. It can be used in professional or private life and help you stay organized while working on projects. A work plan breaks down all the tasks, and assigns different items to specific project members, providing them with individual timelines. It helps project managers to oversee the big picture while managing smaller project parts. A work plan can be represented as the formal roadmap for a project or a structure, visualized with the help of Gantt Charts. Anyway, it should clearly articulate all the required steps to achieve a key goal by setting demonstrable objectives and measurable deliverables. An effective plan is a guiding document aimed to realize an outcome through efficient team collaboration.

ticularly those web sites that gives free discussions, YouTube channels that shows procedures and techniques as the experts use other alternative kitchen materials. WES Advisor (2020) suggests that learning new skills is one of the best ways to become more successful in your career. Whether you are looking for a new career opportunity or would like to move into a more senior role, upgrading your skills can increase your chances of reaching your career goals. In most professions, upgrading your skills is highly valued and is seen as a requirement for many employers. Most jobs are dynamic, constantly changing, and adapting as the field grows. Therefore, employees must be adaptable and up-to-date with the trends and developments in their field. The benefits of upgrad-

Fig. 5. Educational management insights can be drawn from the Trepidations of home economics teachers

ing skills include: Increased self-confidence; Improved marketability and competitiveness: Greater resourcefulness and Better career opportunities. Maclean, Roy (2014) said that one of the most exciting things about being alive now is that things are changing at an incredibly fast rate. Lifelong learning can keep you competitive and arm you with marketable skills. It's also fun, and a great way to expand your inter-

ests, which keeps your brain healthy and staves off aging. Online learning doesn't have to be a pale imitation of "real" in-person learning. It's a whole new way of interacting with learners. What if instead of a boring, predictable series of discussion question posts and assignments, your online courses were a dynamic journey that surprises and engages learners.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study is presented, from the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to unravel the experiences of home economics teachers in teaching the subject as they try to find the best fit learning modalities of the students under their care. To achieve the research objectives, I made use of qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. In adherence to

Cresswell's (2006) guidelines in which open ended questions for interview were applied to get authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to offer their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored.

4.1. Findings—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The trepidations of home economics teachers in determining the best fit learning modalities in their respective classes provided the following themes as a result of the interviews from the participants. The first theme that surfaced, after thorough analysis of the participants' responses was the undefined teaching strategies. The participants really could not identify a single learning or teaching modality that best fit the learners. Most of the participants were giving varied ideas as to what is best to be used as they teach home economics. This must be due to the fact that the home economics teachers had to consider the actual home scenario of the students, whether these students have the expected gadgets to perform home cooking activities. The teachers, therefore relied on the availability of kitchen utensils in the students abode. Another reason is the connectivity of internet, not all the students have internet connections, and some do not even have cellular phones to be used. One comfortable way of implementing the home economics curriculum was the use and distribution of modules to the students. There were too many reasons why a single best fit learning modality is not defined. The second theme that came up upon analysis of the participants' responses was planning variety of lessons. This findings suggests that despite the single topic to be discussed in the module, the teachers were very apprehensive whether the topics in the module is well understood by the students. There were ideas that the students may give another view point on the principles being discussed in the learning material. Having this findings at hand, the home economics teachers need to plan several learning activities that best suit the current availability of student resources. This is a very tedious academic planning that the teachers must do every week as they distribute the modules or even upload some lesson for on line learners. The third theme identified in this area was the limited skills development. The home economics teachers, were all united as they voiced out the feelings about the skills development. They accounted that home economics subject is not about theories in cooking alone. This require the development of hand skills as well as the creativity of the learners. The teachers were all worried that the skills development of the students is at stake. They said that, they are not physically present to supervise the performance of the students. Quite different when there was still the face to face classes, where they can personally correct and check some procedure and techniques in the home economics laboratory. The fourth theme that emerged from the study as to the fears of the teachers in home economics is the limited home cooking gadgets. This is a reality that the teachers must face and agree. Not a single students perfectly have all the cooking gadgets at home. Most of the activities in food preparations described in the module requires a certain kitchen element to come up with the expected output while the student is following the procedures. The fear of teachers in this aspect is on how the students will proceed with the procedures when the demanded kitchen gadget is not available. This takes a lot of creativity and replacement strategies from the students end. Better if the students will always connect with their teachers during food preparations and that the teachers are always available and in good internet signal so that they can communicate and discuss alternative ways to proceed with the

home activity. Pertaining to the coping mechanisms adopted by the teachers in averting their problems, there were two themes that emerged as a result of the data analysis of the gathered information from the home economics teachers. The first theme was on enhancing the theory and on line activities of the students. To limit the significant negative effects of not having the presence of the teachers while performing the home cooking activities, was to give the students more theoretical lessons. This strategy will provide more information on how to do things while at home or using somebody else's kitchen. Additional theoretical integration in the lecture will widen the students understanding the basic principles needed to follow a certain recipe. Alternative resources may also be provided through the lectures, not simple giving the cooking or laboratory procedures. Adding more on line interactions with students will also through chatting, messenger, video calls through zoom, google meet and other alternative on line meetings will alleviate the difficulties un-

4.2. Implications—The educational management insights gained from the participants were as follows: resourcefulness and creativity of the HE teachers, proper work planning and upgrading of on line skills. The first insight of the participants was on resourcefulness and creativity of home economics teachers. At this point in time, the teachers needs to be resourceful in obtaining at hand the necessary information and techniques to facilitate the teaching-learning activities of their students. They must find ways and means to reach out to their students by using their gadgets or cellular phones or lap tops. The teachers must also be more creative in delivering their thoughts through the gadgets they have. The second insight from the study was on the proper work planning. The participants mentioned these during the interviews. Without the proper work plan, the modules they

dergone by students as well as the worried that bothers most of the home economics teachers as to what is happening to the activities they provided to their learners. The second theme identified to avert some the home economics teacher's problems was the idea of open learning concept. As soon as the home economics students are ready to perform their home cooking activities, the teachers were also ready to accept calls and queries from their students while they are performing their respective cooking tasks. In any way possible communication, the teachers were always ready to facilitate the questions of each of their students. This must be some kind of a multitasking-teaching approach, but for the moment, the home economics teachers' best way to make things possible is to use the available on-line facilities. Teachers need to be open on any development coming from the end of the students. A simple call, text message, messenger chats and video calls, that are free of charge is the best possible way of averting such problems, the participants claimed.

distributed will be found useless. There were some procedures provided in the modules, however, these may not be strictly followed. The home economics teachers must do planning way ahead of time and learn to anticipate individual issues coming from the students. The teachers, knowing all the processes to be done, knows more than the students. Teachers must be very open and welcoming to all the questions their students will pose. As the saying goes, 'it pays to plan ahead.' The third insight that emerged from the study was on upgrading of on line skills. This is the reality in this non face to face learning, online or modular learning. Most of the teachers were not ready to use all the available technology in the market. When the pandemic came, most of the home economics teachers wondered how the hand-on activities will be performed at home. Will it be possi-

ble? These are some of their apprehensions for the subject that is too hands on and to face to face in approach. Learning and upgrading of teachers skills for on line use has become a necessity. When there's no possibility of teaching a procedure that is beyond the teachers command. This way, the home economics teachers can download youtube cooking procedures and other platforms and can replace their physical

presence. In terms of modular learning, some of the downloaded informations pertaining to their kitchen tasks can be included in the modules. This eases the worries of the teachers, whether or not the students are doing it right while performing the procedures at home. The participants all agreed to this idea that the necessity to upgrade their technology skills is a big help for them.

4.3. *Future Directions*—Based on the findings of the study, it is significant to implement some of the policies that may be formulated as a result modular learning and the actual experiences of the home economics teachers. Openness to some eventualities will be a great boost to the implementation of the home economics curriculum. Some of the directions of home economics curricular offering in the future may be drawn and executed by the following personnel: The school administrators and home economics coordinators may gain more understanding on the predicaments of the home economics teachers by being more alert and open minded to quickly address some issues in delivering the subject matter to their respective students. These issues may be in the form of technology being used by the teachers. The home economics teachers may be more proactive and developing more of their technological skills to address their individual difficulties in dealing their tech-

nology driven students. By getting along with the speed of the students in doing things on line, they may also be redirected to learn more from the vast opportunities provided by the on line information. The students may be more understanding in dealing with their teacher, particularly in the discussion and explanation of the home economics modules given to them. The students may also be better guides in discovering the wide array of information and cooking procedures and techniques from the internet and other on line technologies. For the future researchers, a similar studies may be conducted in other regions or divisions. The researchers may consider other stakeholders as participants. Studies on the parents contributions in home economics learning of their children. Home creativity in doing the home economics procedures as well as other areas in home economics that may contribute to the enactment of the curriculum and the community.

5. References

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